

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Meeting is being recorded.

Speaker 2

Hello, my thank you for taking your time to participate in this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze and I'm pursuing a master's in software engineering at Blekina Institute of Technology. And I'm investigating how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in open source dependencies they included in their projects. The study focuses on five web frameworks, Django, Next.js, Springboot, Laravel, and Ruby on Rails. And I just want you to know that participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time.

We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information, and we will not share your personal information, such as your name, or e-mail address, or any identifiable details. will not publish them with. And then you can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering. And your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to you or the projects that you present. And the interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the reported data after which they'll be submitted.

So before we start, maybe you can introduce yourself and tell us how long you have been a developer and which of the web frameworks that I'm investigating you've been associated with.

And for how long have you used those web frameworks?

Speaker 1

So Spring Boot.

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

So Spring Boot, sorry. Spring Boot usage is actually quite recent, I think about July 2024 but the spring framework that spring boot is built on top of I was using that sort of from very regularly from December 2015 until I'm using it very regularly I think until about 2,019, and I was using it throughout the the duration of the 1st developer role I heard, which that went from December 2,015 to March 2023. So it was in that timeframe. I mean, but we were obviously we were between spring boot and spring. I've been using the same tool called Maven. Anyway.

Speaker 2

How long have you been a software developer for?

Speaker 1

Wow. Well, my professional career started in 2015. I did an MSc, started an MSc in computing in 2013 when I was first and produced to Java, I think in 2009. Yeah.

Speaker 2

All right. And what exactly do you do? Are you a front-end developer, back-end developer, tester.

Speaker 1

Full stack.

Speaker 2

Full stack.

Speaker 1

I do front-end and back-end. Oh, so regarding front-end, I have experience with React and using dependency management tools in React. Next.js it's a little bit same tools anyway for the purpose of managing dependencies I can tell you a story actually with one of one project that was well a couple of projects actually in one that I was helping with that someone else was a maintainer of and then another project that was my own and there was a recommendation to make the same switch from reusing one dependency management tool to another. So I don't know if you have become aware of. I think it's becoming increasingly more common for people to know about it in the industry that there's a bit of an issue with supply chain attacks at the moment.

Yeah, in particular with one library in the front end ecosystem called NPM. There's been some quite, in fact, I just had a, someone just shared a bit of a, I think it was a LinkedIn post with me today. Apparently even one, one library has been the latest library that seems to have been targeted is called Axios which makes it easier to send HTTP requests. Okay. But yeah, quite a few of these libraries have been targeted like this. So where you have, there's a couple of places where you have to be really, really careful. I mean, so basically with the, there's a couple of different parts to it, so you have to make sure that the name of the dependencies that you install, you have to make sure there's no mistakes there. And now it's becoming, since I've become aware of these attacks, another thing that is worth checking is the version numbers. And there's this term. I don't know if you've heard of this term called version pinning.

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

Where you basically when you choose a dependency, you basically specify I want version X and then you can decide yourself whether you want to update that. I mean different different package managers have different sort of default settings. I think one of the issues with NPM is that it by default will tend to upgrade everything. And that is where that is the danger in a lot of these attacks. And actually, I think an issue with these supply chain attacks is you might not be using, you may not have said I want to use X dependency. But let's say you've used, I don't know, you may have used a dependent given dependency and that dependency itself relies on dependency X. The dependency X might get compromised and you might not even be aware. This is one of the real risks of these tools.

And so with one open source project that I was helping with, I think maybe in November we switched. It was November or December, we basically switched from NPM to PNPM. Okay. So we had to, I think basically, can't quite remember what I had to do, I think. Yeah, we had to sort of, it was a little bit messy. Because some of the-- they use, I think, some part of the configuration is shared, and some of it is different. The way you install a line is different. But also, I think it's more complicated to install the PNPM tool itself. But in this project, actually, for-- I think even from this-- or very early on, we were using, I think, a couple of cybersecurity tools.

I think one was maybe dependabot. The dependabot basically, I think it must be a tool for scanning vulnerabilities that have been reported in some of these kind of PNPM packages. And then you can get emails if it kind of warns you of something's been kind of going to present a vulnerability and worth upgrading. And actually, so I've had a few, I think I get

emails maybe every week or every, whenever it basically detects that something is potentially going to be, cause a problem.

I think that The term tends to be-- but usually there is some reference to CVE number, if you've heard of that. No, I think with all the AI tools, I've heard of a-- there's another danger here. What I went back to is where you have to be really careful is you have to make sure there are no typos in the name of what you install and there's attackers have been trying to exploit this where somebody uses AI to install one of these libraries and the AI gets the name slightly wrong and then it ends up installing a library that an attacker basically created that sounds very similar to the library that the developer intended to install, but it basically contains malware. So that is another sort of, that is another area where you have to be really careful. So I don't ever let, I don't, I think I maybe, when I was first doubling with sort of AI in coding, I was maybe, I was cautious, but I maybe let it, or sort of, I would take whatever it said and install that. Now I always try to check the name of everything. So I think most of these package ones just have an official website where you can basically check, the name of the library.

You can also check things like version, different version numbers that have been released and when they were released. And I think the other reason for using the sort of online databases where there's the official databases for a package that I do is because you can see how popular a library is and is it being well maintained? without actually going back to going back to the I had a second role between I had a second full time role between November 2023 and February 24 and generally there was it wasn't not it was a preferred that if you were going to install anything for a reactive project it had it had to have The minimum number of downloads very recently and it had to have been, I had to have shown that it was updated recently as well.

Speaker 2

So. OK, so for the projects that you have worked on, was anybody responding, was there a security team responsible for ending security issues for all, was it left for all developers? Sorry, I'm asking whether in the projects that you have worked in, was there a security team responsible for handling security issues or was it up to the whole team?

Speaker 1

In one of those projects, there was a security person. Yeah. Oh, that's why. So we had to install SEM group, I think. Is SEM group another tool for helping with? catching sort of, I don't, well, there was SEM group, I think. Husky was another tool I wanted to install as well. Okay.

Speaker 2

And how are security, how were security issues handled? The reports, how were they handled? Like if you got a report that there were some vulnerabilities within your projects, how would they handle? Oh.

Speaker 1

I think probably I can't remember what trying to think. I suppose someone would have to update the they'd have to. They'd have to basically check for a safe version number and update that, and then everyone else that's working on the same project. Well, I think basically if you're using like a version, you have a file that kind of says what version you're using, then that gets pushed to Git. One person just has to update that and then basically the other developers just kind of they one day kind of pull the latest updates and they pull that file in and then you basically they have to do like as you have to basically install it as if you're installing it for the first time so it updates everything that's what we had to do when we well that's also what we had to do when we switched from using NPM to the NPM okay.

Speaker 2

Okay. And what influences the decision to update to newer versions of dependencies within your project?

Speaker 1

Well, I think maybe if it could be, it could be, yeah, if someone's seen like if there's been like a major headline like about a tool that's been compromised or If Dependabot, basically, if Dependabot kind of flags something, that might be the other, the other sort of thing. So those are the main sort of two avenues.

Speaker 2

And how do you check the maintenance of dependencies within your projects? Because it's common for some dependents to be abandoned by their creators. So how do you know that all the dependents you are using, they are still being maintained in the case of vulnerability or case they can address it?

Speaker 1

Sorry, I didn't quite hear of the.

Speaker 2

Okay, I said, how do you check the maintenance of dependencies in your projects? Because it's common for open source dependencies to be abandoned by their creators.

And when they abandon their dependencies, they stop supporting them or doing any maintenance work on them. Yeah. Yeah. How do you check that the dependencies you're using are still being maintained?

Speaker 1

Oh, I, well. I think I was telling you this before, like, are you asking like, I mean, I tend to check before I'm going to install the dependency in the 1st place.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

But after you are using it now, I haven't actually before. I haven't come across a situation where anything's been abandoned halfway through. Okay. I haven't actually. come across that situation but I would if it looked like something had been very recently abandoned though oh it wasn't very popular I wouldn't install it anyway but uh I I suppose you just have to keep that's an interesting one I you just is it something you have to do manually you have to just like go into the database website and see if something has been. I mean, that sounds doesn't sound like an easy issue to deal with when you're so busy and you're working with a lot of different dependencies. It's that's it's an important issue that you raised, actually, because I've never really considered that.

Speaker 2

Okay. Alright. And you mentioned using GitHub dependabot to check for vulnerabilities within your project. How long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies after you discover that they are vulnerable?

Speaker 1

Oh, that, I don't know if anyone's actually done that. I haven't done that yet. Okay. Well, I suppose it depends on what you need to do because if you're going to It depends if you like, in theory, you shouldn't have to do much. You just have to, you're not going to change the dependency and it's not going to cause any broken code changes. It's just a matter of usually updating your file that says what version of the dependency you're using. Then you just kind of install that and kind of push it to Git and then everyone else can do that. If you're going to have to, if you're going to have to update the actual code, it could take a bit longer, I suppose. If there's breaking changes in the code, this is a result of the change.

Speaker 2

You mentioned using JavaScript libraries within your project and sometimes the dependence is there, they get like duplicated, like they are no longer being maintained. And how do you handle that?

Speaker 1

How do you work?

Speaker 2

How do you handle that when you have a dependence that's no longer being maintained or that's to be created in your within your debit industry?

Speaker 1

Oh, I think with the with Java. Java, they tend to, ah, so with Java, as you can. tells you when something's been deprecated. That's a kind of links to the last question. You have to like. So actually this links back to the last question. You're asking if that cause, if it's going to cause breaking changes, you have to go and basically re kind of do whatever you basically have to rewrite. You have to pull out, you might need to pull out that dependency and then rewrite that code and kind of make sure all the tests and stuff is still going to pass.

Speaker 2

Okay, so certain communities like I'm coming from the Python and Django community. And sometimes when a library is no longer being maintained, community members can step up to take over the maintenance of that project. Is this something that happens within the Java community? Okay.

Speaker 1

The main thing that I've used, the main library I've used in the Java community is that are open source, I think. I'll probably, I think it's paid companies that maintain. Well, like companies, they basically, they have revenue streams coming in from other kind of products. And so they definitely have a team of maintainers anyway. And I'm not kind of, I haven't come across No issue. I mean, this is one of the nice things about Java is it's generally quite stable.

Speaker 2

Okay. Okay. And if you encounter, if you encountered that same issue, like within the JavaScript community community, you mentioned using some JavaScript library.

Speaker 1

And the what about those JavaScript libraries?

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

Well, sorry, what was the question?

Speaker 2

Okay, so I'd say, Okay, sometimes developers or companies, they take over maintenance of dependence they rely on, which is easier when it's coming from within your ecosystem, for example, for you in Java. Would you step up to maintain, say, a dependency in the JavaScript community, given that you do use the dependence from them? despite focusing on Java, and how easy or difficult would that be for you?

Speaker 1

Oh, you're asking if I would kind of be willing to step up was a maintainer.

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

I never thought. Yeah, I've never thought about that. I mean, yeah, I would. Well, I if it's something very It depends if it's something small and I might, if it's something really big, maybe not. If it's small at all, then I might do. Yes, I mean, but I would think that because I would have to basically make sure I'm comfortable with various cybersecurity kind of, well, like basic security sort of like account protection measures are in place. But I'm going to do that. Like what I was going to do is I'd want to make sure like things like two-factor authentication is switched on, so my account is protected and there's less chance of my-- and so I did take over as a maintainer. I'd want to make sure that it's not going to be compromised or I'd have to do whatever I can to minimize it being compromised.

So I'd also put-- I'd make sure there was a-- I think you have to be careful with repository permissions and code reviews and things like that that's a way of basically monitoring what like if anyone's going to try and if someone can try and compromise your code by submitting a pull request so that would be something that I'd have to be keeping on top of.

Speaker 2

And what practices and tools are in place for supply chain attacks mitigation in a project?

Speaker 1

That was, those were some of the ones that I mentioned earlier.

Speaker 1

I think Dependabot is the main one. Okay. Because that sort of tells you when, that warns you when something's been reported as vulnerable. I don't know how. That's the main one that we're using at the moment. I think there's a few different tools like that, but that's the one that we're using at the moment. As far as I'm aware, so far we've been lucky. We haven't, we haven't kind of dealt, we haven't been compromised yet. We haven't kind of pulled in anything that has been compromised. So far we have been lucky, but there was, I think in the personal project I was doing, I was looking at something like maybe Husky and then I think I was looking at some libraries like Husky or Prettier. And it's like that same evening, apparently they've been compromised. That was quite scary. I suppose the other part of mitigation is making sure that you double check things like versioning, like manually checking to make sure the version is what version you're going to install and making sure the name is correct and making sure it's listed in the official kind of online database.

Hopefully, hopefully my answers have been helpful for you. I don't know.

Speaker 2

And okay, What if you face, what challenges, if any, have you faced which hindered you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 1

Sorry.

Speaker 2

Are there any challenges that you face when trying to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 1

Address what dependencies?

Speaker 2

Challenges that you may face when trying to maybe address vulnerable reports on vulnerable dependencies within your projects.

Speaker 1

Do you say vulnerable?

Speaker 2

I'm saying are there any challenges that you might face when dealing with vulnerable dependencies?

Speaker 1

Well, I suppose the issue you might run into is if there's mismatches between you. If the people have got different versions of things installed, that can cause problems. I think I'll get back to it because it's actually so we've had some issues. We've had issues in work projects actually where even just the version of Java being different can cause a lot of problems in a project. That did cause a few issues because you can't even just even compiling the project just won't work. Then you have to update even the version of Java and the dependencies there just to even get the project to run.

Speaker 2

And what do you think would help to make the process of dealing with vulnerable dependencies in your project?

Speaker 1

So vulnerable dependencies.

Speaker 2

What will help to you address them?

Speaker 1

Oh. Oh, God! That's gone a bit blank.

Speaker 2

Okay. I'm asking what would make the process easier of dealing with a vulnerable dependencies.

Speaker 1

What make it easier?

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

But I think part of the problem is, well, the issue at the moment is that every time when you update it and then you have to reinstall everything and then everybody else has to reinstall everything. And that can be, it's just that that is a main inconvenience. If there's anything that can be done to make that part of it simpler. Then like that would just make the whole thing easier to. I don't know. Yeah, that I don't know if that was a helpful answer. Okay.

Speaker 2

OK.

Speaker 2

And what do you have? What recommendations do you have for other developers on how they can manage open source dependencies to mitigate supply chain attack?

Speaker 1

Yeah, advice to other developers. Yeah, kind of. I think I've mentioned this a few times throughout the interview. I mean, kind of making sure just the user that you have to be very cautious, especially when AI says it wants to install everything. I mean, make sure that you check that the name for a start is even correct and it's uh the the version number that's and if you can lock down if you basically if you see that a version is recent well maintained and it's safe and you have the you can basically just say I want to use this version and I I don't want you to auto update it. And that means that if it gets auto updated and that package is being compromised, if you said you don't want to, you basically want to stick with a particular version, then it won't, it shouldn't update that version. And then if there is an attack, you should be immune to that attack in theory, but it's a, that's, I don't know if there's any way to say, I don't know if there's any way to control some dependencies. That's where it gets a bit complicated. But in terms of the dependencies you're using, you should definitely lock down the version to something that's safe in a used by a sort of it's got a good usage number, fairly recent sort of update as well. So yeah.

And yeah, that is a this term is a is I would recommend every developer is aware of this type of attack called slot squatting. Because the last thing you want is to basically install something that is pretending to be the library. You are actually wanting to install what you installed was basically malware that or they gave a name of the library that is very similar to the library you wanted to install.

Speaker 2

All right, thank you so much for taking your time to spin the interview.

Speaker 1

You're welcome.

Speaker 2

All right, I'll stop recording now.